

GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE OBJECT AS A MEMBER OF THE SENTENCE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Abstract. The present work is devoted to the comparative-typological study of the objects as an object distributor of the predicate in the Uzbek language in comparison with English.

Key words. Sentence, comparison, predicate, determine Uzbek and English language.

Introduction.

The relevance of the topic. The modern period in the development of linguistics is characterized by the rapid flourishing of linguistic theories in general and syntactic ones in particular. In works on general linguistics, language is considered as a means of forming, expressing and communicating thoughts. However, in modern linguistic theories, the main provisions of general linguistics are not always taken into account consistently and sufficiently. Many linguists consider the main function of language to be a communicative function, while forgetting that language can be a means of communication only because thinking is carried out with its help, the most essential feature of a sentence is its ability to form and express thought.

Main part.

The object is one of the leading minor members of the sentence; the grammatical essence and semantic function of the object.

An object is a syntactically driven member of a sentence. Its position and design in the Uzbek language is controlled by the predicate, and in English the predicate determines the choice of the case or prepositional case form to which the object is presented. In languages with object agreement, the object is the controller (or one of the controllers) of the predicate agreement with the subject. Academician Ivan Ivanovich Meshchaninov and some other theorists of ergativity syntax, following him, believe that in such languages the direct object is the third main member of the sentence.

In contrast to the circumstance, the object in both Uzbek and English, being “strongly controlled”, objects the mandatory valence of the predicate. For example: Samovorchi uning ustiga sandalini qo‘ydi va uni ustiga ko‘rpani to‘shadi.

Zoya Dadoboyga hayrat bilan qaradi.

Zebining niyatini darrov anglagan Yunusbobo hammani ishga chorladi

They all loved Arthur for his own sake as his mother's crowded round him, kissing his hands and dress with passionate grief. [1, 50]

1) The weather was hot, and the sheet of folded paper that he pulled out was not only dirty and crumbled, but damp.

2) He stood for a moment shuffling his feet uneasily; then put up one hand and scratched the back of his head [2, 328]

In English, the following types of objects differ in structure:

a) simple,

b) composite (analytical);

c) combined.

1) simple (expressed by a proper name, an actualized group of a common noun and an actualizer, or a pronoun);

2) analytical - expressed by a combination of a service word (preposition or postposition) with a significant one; usually indirect objects are arranged in this way: Examples:

Ertalab ona bolalarga kechasi uyida sodir bo'lgan voqeani aytib berdi.

U ham o'z nafsidan (hayotidan) qo'rqardi.

"I don't want your money", he said roughly.

"I'd have done more than that for him". He'd been good to me - God help me. [3, 311]

Montanelli Arturga o'girilib, unga butun oqshom uning yuzidan tushmagan mulohazali, xavotirli ifoda bilan qaradi.

Montanelli turned to Arthur with the intent and brooding look.

Bir kuni Mirzoabdullo Korishikambadan yuz ming Buxoro tangasini so'radi.

3) combined, including composed, for example:

Shavkat Iskandar bilan Qurbonni tanishtirdi (bir-birlari bilan); Shuhrat Iskandarni Qurbon bilan tanishtirdi; Shavkat Iskandarni Qurbon bilan tanishtirdi;

Gulandon Ra'no bilan Zeboni (bir-birlari bilan) tanishtirdi.

Zoya yana bir stakan suv berdi.

Artur o'girilib, Montanellining ko'ziga tik qaradi.

Arthur turned round and looked straight into Montanelli's eyes. [4, 24]

Composite, which mainly include combinations of words, phrases and other constructions: Examples:

Azizim, menda nimani ko'rding

Menga yuragingni berib, yuragimni mendan olganingnimi? Mirza Tursnzoda.

- Eshaklar! - deb pichirladi Artur kulib turgan ko'zlarini Montanelli Voynichga, qaratib.

What idiotic people! Arthur whispered, looking up with dancing eyes. [4, 21]

The Gadfly responded with a violent attack on the new Pontificate and all its supporters, especially on Montanelli, who the cautiously hinted had probably consented to the panegyric on himself. [5, 134]

Just look at the line of his eye-brows! [5, 21]

Uning qoshlariga qarang! [6, 57]

With verbs with an inconspicuous object, the latter expresses a collapsed (nominalized) predication (with the meaning of a fact, situation, or proposition). These are verbs with phase, modal, inter-event, perceptual, mental and propositive meanings. An inconspicuous object is canonically expressed by a subordinate clause, an explanatory, infinitive turn, with a predicative name or an inconspicuous pronoun (this is, what, something...):

Gemma followed the two men out of the room and presently returned with an egg beaten up in milk. Take this, please, she said with mild authority and sat down again to her knitting. [7, 168].

Conclusion.

Indeed, at a time when the circumstances for our people's spiritual growth are being established in our nation, the study of languages should likewise serve this aim. Our national linguistics, which has chosen the route of autonomous growth, is presently on the way to determining the role of language in human social activity, exploring its communicative nature and anthropocentric qualities while adopting sophisticated ideas typical of world linguistics.

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